

Working paper: research outline

WP6: Legitimate crisis governance and economic sustainability

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LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA No 101061550.

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Document information

CALL REFERENCE	HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY 01
PROPOSAL NUMBER	101061550
FULL TITLE	Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems
ACRONYM	LEGITIMULT
PROJECT START DATE	1 October 2022
PROJECT END DATE	30 September 2025

Document history

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION	CONTRIBUTORS
1	09/09/2023	Elaboration	Marius Guderjan, Ana Herrero, Mario Kölling, Johanna Schnabel
2	16/09/2023	Revision	Theresia Morandell
3	29/09/2023	incorporation of the comments	Marius Guderjan, Ana Herrero, Mario Kölling, Johanna Schnabel

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1. Introduction

COVID-19 was a major public health crisis that triggered large scale state interventions to contain the negative impact on people – in particular the high number of deaths. Consequently, many studies on the crisis management of the pandemic focus on governments' efforts to prevent health care services and hospitals from collapsing, procure medical equipment and vaccines, implement quarantines, deliver testing and contact tracing, and to provide education and childcare in the light of school and nursery closures. The extraordinary circumstances in times of crisis management usually do not follow the normal rules of procedure but require fast and extensive responses (Boin et al. 2016). This raised serious concerns about the legitimacy of state interventions in regard to public restrictions, vaccination programmes and the enforcement of lockdowns. However, the virus did not only impact people's physical and mental well-being, but the restrictions on public life also brought severe social and economic consequences as many shops, factories and service providers had to temporarily close or reduce their activities. It was imperative

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to ensure that the health crisis would not turn into a systemic economic crisis with long-lasting damages for labour and financial markets (Bofinger et al. 2020). Because crises tend to cause reductions in consumption, investment and credit transactions, without substantial and timely actions, the economic downturn would have been greatly amplified (Gourinchas 2020). Governments across Europe introduced a wide range of policies to compensate citizens and businesses by maintaining households' disposable income, enabling short-time work, ensuring cash flows and limiting financial obligations. Fiscal and economic measures therefore made up some of the earliest and most extensive responses and varied tremendously in timing, breadth and scope (Weder di Mauro 2020).

National governments tend to have broad powers to tackle a crisis. While several of federal and multilevel states centralised policy responses to contain the spreading of the pandemic (either by consensus or not) (Bloom et al. 2022; Chattopadhyay and Knüpling 2022: 284 et seq.; Steytler 2022: 401 et seq.; Vampa 2021), merely assuming a centralisation of powers during the pandemic would overly simplify the realities of multilevel crisis management. As COVID-19 and restriction policies strongly impacted on the social and economic cohesion of local localities and regions across Europe, subnational governments were responsible for economic recovery and supported the needs and living conditions of their citizens (European Committee of the Regions 2021: 64 et seq.). The European Committee of the Regions (2021: 64) argued that “[...] the misapplication of multilevel governance, and therefore the limited involvement of local and regional authorities, can undermine democratic ‘legacy and legitimacy’.” Considering that different tiers of government, including national, subnational and supranational levels, played an essential part in supporting individuals and businesses, we are interested in understanding how multilevel systems shaped the legitimacy of crisis management in terms of governance and results. For this purpose, this working paper introduces the research design that allows us to examine the impact of political de/centralisation and intergovernmental coordination on the design, implementation and results of social and economic responses to COVID-19 across different levels. We will firstly give a brief overview of our theoretical Framework. Secondly, we will present the research questions and hypotheses for our qualitative and quantitative analysis as well as the methodological approach. And finally, we will give an overview over the state of our research and next steps.

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2. Research design

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 Political Legitimacy

We start our theoretical framework with defining and operationalising the political legitimacy of policy measures. This relates to the relationship between state and citizens and questions about why and under what conditions people believe in the rightfulness of state and support government (Barker 1990: 2 et seq.). Political legitimacy can rest on either moral and ethical arguments of rightfulness, fairness, equality and justice, sociological (normative perspective) or people’s attitudes, beliefs and acceptance of political authority (empirical perspective) (Bekkers and Edwards 2007: 38; Weiler 2012: 826; Levitov 2016; Tallberg and Zürn 2019: 583; Schmidt 2020: 30).¹ Easton (1965) further distinguishes between diffuse support for a political system and specific support for government performance and outputs. For Easton (1975: 437), specific support is “a response to the authorities” and only indirectly depends on the input of people. Hence, instead of considering *input-oriented legitimacy* (see Scharpf 1999), we assess legitimacy against the ability to generate public welfare and the quality of democratic procedures (Sternberg 2015: 615; Strebel et al. 2019: 489-490).

Notions of ‘good governance’ can support the legitimacy of governments and their performance by ensuring that office holders are accountable for their actions, follow the rule of law, provide transparent information about policy-making and implementation to the public, are responsive to the demands of citizens, and produce effective and efficient outputs (Keping 2018: 5-6). In democracies, good governance is based on the active participation and input of citizens (Keping 2018: 6), which applies to the countries we investigate. As the OECD suggests: “In times of crisis, public governance matters more than ever. Governance arrangements have played a critical role in countries’ immediate responses to COVID-19, and will continue to be crucial both during the recovery and in building a “new normal” in the years to come.”²

¹ Beetham (1991: 16 et seq.) identifies three dimensions that contribute to the legitimacy of modern states: 1) the conformity of rules; 2) the justifiability of the rules through shared beliefs; and 3) the consent of the subordinate. In Gilley’s (2012: 694) words, “a state is more legitimate the more that its citizens treat it as holding and exercising power rightfully, meaning in a manner that is consistent with rules and laws (legality), that is morally justified (justification), and to which they have actively consented (consent)”.

² <https://www.oecd.org/governance/public-governance-responses-to-covid19/>

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Therefore, we analyse to what extent governance processes (*throughput-oriented legitimacy*) and the effectiveness of measures (*output-oriented legitimacy*) enhanced or reduced the political legitimacy of the social and economic responses to COVID-19 in multilevel systems.

Throughput-oriented legitimacy looks inside the ‘black box’ of governance and the extent to which procedures are applied fairly, impartially and equally for all (Schmidt 2020: 25; see also Rohstein 2009: 325). For Schmidt (2020: 40 et seq.), throughput legitimacy depends on administrations’ efficacy (efficient governance or competent management); accountability (public justification of actions); transparency (public access to information about decision-making processes); openness (engagement with concerned members of the public); and inclusiveness (ensuring fairness and balance of interest representation). We also focus on the legality of government actions and whether they were consistent with existing rules and laws or whether governments exceeded or contravened their authority as an important factor for throughput legitimacy (cf. Beetham 1991: 16).

Throughput legitimacy complements the need to perform in line with citizens’ needs (Schmidt 2020: 54). To assess how the effectiveness of social and economic measures contributed to political legitimacy of multilevel crisis management, we also analyse the *output-oriented legitimacy*. This refers to the ability of governance systems to meet the interests of their jurisdictions timely and adequately (Bekkers and Edwards 2007: 45; Piattoni 2010: 213; Schmidt 2020, pp. 31-33). The prioritisation of objectives, choice of adequate measures and procedures and distribution of tasks raises further questions about the distributions of the benefits and costs of political decisions (Sternberg 2015: 621).

2.1.2 Political Legitimacy in Multilevel Systems

Our research aims to find out how multilevel systems shape the political legitimacy of crisis management. Multilevel systems are characterised by dispersion of political, legislative and fiscal authority (cf. Schneider’s 2003: 33; Bolleyer and Thorlakson 2012: 569; Keil and Anderson 2018: 91). How they operate in practice depends on constitutional, legal, and institutional provisions (Jeffery 2000: 3) as well as on the allocation of resources and authority over revenues and expenditures (Cheema and Rondinelli 2007: 6-7). Central governments control major financial means to engage in counter-cyclical spending, provide social assistance and deliver unemployment policies (Maher et al. 2020; Rocco et al. 2020; Capano and Lippi

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2021) which allowed them to respond to COVID-19. Yet, even though subnational governments depended on federal transfers either in the form of shared taxes, ad hoc grants or fiscal equalisation payments, they control significant financial resources enabling them to pass and implement measures (Chattopadhyay et al. 2022). In consideration of existing research on federalism and decentralisation, what may we expect of the impact of multilevel systems on the political legitimacy of the Covid-19 crisis management?

First, empowering subnational legislatures and executives can provide citizens with new opportunities to participate in subnational elections and policy-making for their territorial jurisdictions (Piattoni 2010: 192). The literature on federalism typically suggests that policies and public services better reflect citizens' needs when designed and implemented by the lowest level of government capable of performing these tasks effectively (Oates 1972; Musgrave 1959; Buchanan 1965). Tailored measures can increase commitment and ownership, allow for innovative solutions and the sharing of best practices (Besley and Case 1995; Ayala et al. 2021). Several studies (OECD 2020; Saunders 2021; 2022; Chattopadhyay and Knüpling 2022) suggested that regional and local governments provided fast and targeted bottom-up responses to the pandemic, including health care, social welfare and education, that were subsequently adopted in other jurisdictions. Notwithstanding the benefits of decentralisation, centralised actions can ensure consistency and cheaper provision of services, in particular when territorial spillovers and inequalities are high (Oates 1972; Prud'homme 1994; Treisman 2007; Bednar 2009; Feld and Schaltegger 2017). To contain the spreading of the pandemic, a number of federal and multilevel states declared a state of emergency, which enabled a centralisation of competences either by consensus (e.g., Spain (Kölling 2022: 208) and Belgium) or not (e.g., France and Italy) (Vampa 2021) (Bloom et al. 2022; Chattopadhyay and Knüpling 2022: 284 et seq.; Steytler 2022: 401 et seq.). In light of this debate between centralisation and decentralisation, we need to consider how decentralised policy measures enhanced or lowered the throughput and output legitimacy of crisis management. We therefore examine the extent to which decentralisation affected the throughput and output legitimacy of the social and economic responses.

Secondly, although in multilevel systems governments can in principle decide unilaterally within their area of exclusive competence, decentralisation usually does not provide subnational governments with complete autonomy (cf. Rodden 2004: 486; Cheema and Rondinelli 2007). In order to respond to common policy challenges that spill over across different jurisdictions and levels, governments usually coordinate

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their actions to varying degrees in order to prevent and reduce incoherence, inconsistency, contradiction, fragmentation, redundancy, negative externalities, harmful competition and conflict (Kennett 1998; Peters 1998; 2015; Cameron and Simeon 2002; Braun 2006; Watts 2008; Bouckaert et al. 2010; Jensen et al. 2014; Parker 2015; Wasserfallen 2015). Coordination can allow governments to realise economies of scale (Painter 1998; Bouckaert et al. 2010), engage in policy learning (Füglister 2012; Füglister and Wasserfallen 2014; Wallner 2014) and achieve equity in public service delivery (Thorlakson 2003: 16; Bolleyer 2006). The benefits and cost-efficiency of coordination are particularly visible in times of crisis (King 1984; Treisman 1999; De Mello 2000; Boin and Bynander 2016; Martinez-Vazquez et al. 2017; Migone 2020). Hence, we consider not only the decision-making and implementation of policy measures by individual governments but also the governance arrangements between levels of government (cf. Burgess 2006: 138; McEwen and Petersohn 2015: 192; Hooghe et al. 2016; Behnke 2018: 36). Institutional incentives increase the capacities to pursue common objectives, to coordinate decentralised jurisdictions (Benz 2013: 73) and to deal with conflicts and interdependencies (Bolleyer and Thorlakson 2012: 566-567). This can involve formal bicameral legislatures, informal arrangements without legally binding effect, such as intergovernmental councils (Broschek 2011: 545; Hueglin 2013: 39; Behnke 2018: 38), informal practices or ad hoc exchanges (cf. Benz 2009: 51; Hueglin and Fenna 2010: 50; Benz and Broschek 2013: 7; McEwen et al. 2015: 16). Some multilevel polities also adopted a functional division of powers according to which the central level passes laws that are subsequently implemented by the subnational units (Broschek, 2011: 545; Poirier and Saunders 2015: 446; Bolleyer 2018: 47-48). However, coordination can also slow down decision-making, cause conflicts, increase the complexity of decision-making, and blur responsibility and accountability for outcomes (Benz and Papadopoulos, 2006; Papadopoulos and Piattoni, 2019; Peters and Pierre, 2004; Scharpf, 1988). This may obstruct crisis management processes and outputs (Caravita et al., 2021). Whereas some studies concluded that the need to coordinate their responses impeded federal systems in their ability to take fast and effective decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Paquet and Schertzer 2020; Navarro and Velasco 2022), other research argued that effective crisis management depended on the coordination of actions rather than on the de/centralisation or the nature of the multilevel system (OECD 2020; Hegele and Schnabel 2021: 1070; Chattopadhyay and Knüpling 2022: 294; Schnabel et al. 2023). We therefore examine the extent to which intergovernmental coordination affected the throughput and output legitimacy of the social and economic responses.

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2.2 Research question(s) and hypotheses and Data collection

2.2.1 Qualitative analysis

Exploring the impact of decentralisation and intergovernmental coordination in crisis management offers the possibility of answering the following two research questions in our qualitative analysis:

- Did intergovernmental coordination decrease transparency, accountability and efficacy, while strengthening the effectiveness and territorial consistency in COVID-19 crisis management in mitigating the social and economic impact of COVID-19?
- Was decentralisation more transparent, accountable and efficient as well as effective and territorially consistent in mitigating the social and economic impact of COVID-19 than centralised approaches?

In line with our theoretical framework and research questions, we posit the following two hypotheses:

- A high degree of intergovernmental coordination reduces the transparency, accountability and efficacy of crisis management but increases effectiveness as well as territorial consistency of crisis management.
- A high degree of decentralised decision-making increases the transparency, accountability and efficacy but reduces the effectiveness and territorial consistency of crisis management.

The level of decentralised decision-making will be measured on the basis of data included in the Regional Authority Index. This index systematically examined the level of self-rule and shared rule by looking at direct regional participation in *law-making* and veto powers; shared *executive control* over the implementation of policies; *fiscal control* over the distribution of tax revenues across the whole state; *borrowing control* over national and regional borrowing levels; and impact on *constitutional reform* (Hooghe et al., 2008, p. 131-135; Hooghe et al., 2016, pp. 26-29).

During our initial research and based on primary and secondary resources we identified a wide range of relevant measures that existed in all our selected states:

Social measures are typically cash transfers to improve the economic situation of households/individuals or to prevent poverty (e.g., safety net programmes). An example are child benefits which governments

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can increase during a crisis to assist families. Social measures can also be debt/contract relief to stop financial obligations for households (e.g., preventing services like water from being cut, or banning evictions).

Economic measures are measures such as loan and credit guarantees. They provide financial support to companies to stabilise the economy. Economic measures can also be furlough schemes or debt/contract relief to stop financial obligations for companies and the self-employed.

Fiscal measures are measures such as tax cuts or exemptions that governments use to stabilise the economy. A decrease in personal income tax, for example, aims at increasing consumption, which in turn can have a stimulating effect on the economy. Similarly, a reduction in the tax burden of the corporate sector can stimulate investment.

2.2.2 Quantitative analysis

In order to evaluate the implementation of economic, social and fiscal policies that aimed at mitigating the impact of the pandemic in different countries, we apply econometric and impact evaluation techniques and identify the most relevant factors informing these measures. In this quantitative analysis, we are studying whether MLG had any impact on the size of the economic support, income support and debt relief that each country implemented during the first three years of the pandemic. In this regard and based on our theoretical framework we will be answering the following research question:

Did decentralisation in crisis management increase the size of the economic support, income support and debt relief that each country implemented during the first three years of the pandemic?

In line with this research question, we posit the following hypotheses:

- A high degree of decentralised decision-making decreases the size of the economic support.
- A high degree of decentralised decision-making decreases the size of income support.
- A high degree of decentralised decision-making decreases the size of debt relief.

All three hypotheses are based on the assumption that decentralised countries implement measures that are – to a larger extent than centralised nations – tailored to the specific needs and preferences of each individual territory. This result is expected to be more relevant in a context of an asymmetric impact of the pandemic within countries.

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In order to operationalise our independent variable, we rely on the Regional Authority Index, the share of subnational expenditure and the share of subnational tax revenue. For our dependent variables we will use data provided by the Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker, as well as use IMF and Eurostat databases.

As control variables, we included a vector of socio-economic, financial, institutional and health indicators that could potentially explain the intensity of anti-COVID public policies:

- Economic: unemployment, per capita GDP, weight of self-employed within total active population, share of tourism in national GDP. (Eurostat)
- Financial: public debt as a share of national GDP. (Eurostat, IMF database)
- Institutional: ideology of national government and severity of the lockdown Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker, IMF, OECD).
- Health: number of deceased due to Covid-19 and number of confirmed cases (Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker).

For this purpose, we created an unbalanced panel data set that includes 15 periods (quarterly data, when available, from January 2020 to September 2022) and 31 European countries.

2.3 Methodological approach

2.3.1 Qualitative analysis

We are conducting qualitative case studies which allows for in-depth examination of the legitimacy of crisis management with regard to social, fiscal, and economic measures. In order to compare the political legitimacy of the social and economic responses to COVID-19 in a variety of different multilevel polities, we will focus on France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Poland, the United Kingdom (UK) and the EU. This sample includes all EU Member States with more than 40 million inhabitants and states with different territorial structures. We will also apply our theoretical and methodological model to the EU, as the role of the supranational level in multilevel crisis management, especially in terms of economic measures, has been instrumental. We further include the UK to see if EU membership has an impact on crisis management.

We examine the impact of the decentralisation and intergovernmental coordination on the governance and effectiveness of selected social and economic responses to COVID-19 in multilevel systems. For this

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purpose, we identify whether decisions to make a policy measure and its implementation were centralised, concurrent or decentralised. We also examine whether intergovernmental coordination was based on joint law making and different degrees of consultation between governments.

Considering our theoretical discussion and the context of our research, as part of our **throughput dimension**, we analyse in the governance and implementation 1) the **accountability and transparency** and 2) the **efficacy** of decision-making and implementation. Our **output dimension** focuses on 1) the **effectiveness** and 2) the **territorial consistency** in terms of the burden and benefits of a measure.

Accountability and transparency: The indicator analyses to what extent legislative oversight rights were curtailed and if specific parliamentary oversight mechanisms were employed during the crisis to ensure parliamentary control over decisions and implementation of social, fiscal and economic measures. We will also analyse the legal sources of decision-making. Furthermore, the indicator explores to what extent the audit office was able to effectively assess the financial risks associated with government measures and could effectively advocate for sound fiscal performance management.

Efficacy: Effective decision-making and implementation requires the necessary administrative capacity as well as the political capacity. Effective decision-making also includes clear distribution of responsibilities and inter-ministerial coordination. Administrative capacity for implementation refers to the availability of resources and staff that implement measures. It relies on organisational competences and policy instruments of governments to implement measures, e.g., to prevent the misuse of economic aid or corruption.

Effectiveness: This indicator examines the appropriateness of the measures in terms of their timeliness, scope and accuracy. Was the timeliness, scope and accuracy of the social, fiscal and economic measures sufficient to mitigate harmful and disruptive social, economic and fiscal consequences of the pandemic? We will measure the indicator on the basis of economic performance (e.g., GDP) unemployment figures and insolvencies.

Territorial consistency: This indicator focuses on the territorial distribution of measures in terms of the burden and benefits. We will assess the indicator based on criteria applied for the distribution of support in order to detect within-country regional differences:

- In the case of economic measures, since they were targeted to cushion the fall in economic activity and the latter was hit to a greater extent in territories in which tourism and hostelry

absorb larger shares of the economy, territorial consistency will be measured according to the fall in regional GDP.

- Regarding income measures, their purpose was to mitigate the abrupt decrease in household income, especially in those households suffering from unemployment and those previously working in the informal economy. We will assess the territorial consistency of these measures with the share of households without market income.

2.3.2 Quantitative analysis

According to our theoretical framework, we apply the following econometric technique and identify the most relevant factors informing social, economic and fiscal measures.

Our first dependent variable is based on the “Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker”, which provides a wide range of indicators to evaluate the intensity of measures (stringency index). These indexes are ordinal. Although the Oxford data base provides information on the intensity of measures on a daily basis, our explanatory variables –such as GDP, public debt, etc.- are only available quarterly or annually. Therefore, we aggregate daily data in quarters and obtain an average daily measure, turning our initial discrete variable into a continuous one. However, it is important to take into account that all the values of this variable are non-negative (zero or above) and with an upper bound of 100 for economic measures and 2 for both income and debt relief measures. Therefore, our optimal econometric approach is a censored regression model such as the Tobit model, which only allows predicted outcomes within the upper and the lower limits.

In order to further understand the explanatory factors of the size of the social, economic and fiscal adopted by each country, we will run an analysis similar to the previous one but based on a different endogenous variable: **change in public spending**. Separate estimations will be run in order to capture different social, economic and fiscal measures: direct aid to families, direct aid to companies, social expenditure, debt relief for families or companies, tax deferrals, etc. (Eurostat).

The dependent variable is expressed in nominal per capita Euros. Therefore, we rely on a continuous variable that allows us to use the classical regression linear model. As in the multinomial ordered logit

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estimations, the explanatory variables include a vector of economic, financial and governance/institutional arrangements (multilevel institutions as provided by the Regional Authority Index or the share of subnational expenditure/revenue). The development of the health crisis (infection and death rates) and the intensity of the lockdown will provide control variables. Budgetary variables are usually characterized by strong inertia, making static econometric approaches unsuitable to capture the dependence of the endogenous variable from on previous periods (Lago et al., 2018; Ayala et al., 2021). In order to address the autoregressive behavior of our dependent variable, a dynamic panel data model will be used.

Furthermore, we will focus on the impact of MLG on the timing of the adoption of measures. To that end we will use different dependent variables to measure the adoption of different policy measures. Following Toshkov et al. (2022), for each of these variables, two different measures will be calculated:

- a) The cumulative number of confirmed COVID-19 cases at the time of policy adoption.
- b) The number of days between the first confirmed COVID-19 case and policy adoption.

In addition, we also consider an additional measure aimed at assessing the capacity of the countries to maintain selected policy measures, such as lockdowns:

- c) The duration (in days) of the adopted measure relative to the number of confirmed COVID-19 cases.

Our dependent variables will be obtained mostly from the “Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker” database.

Our explanatory variables include institutional settings of the countries under analysis as well as an array of social and economic factors acting as controls. The Regional Authority Index provides one of our key explanatory variables (Hooghe et al., 2008; 2016) to measure the self-rule and shared rule exercised by regional governments, as well as other alternative measures of power decentralisation. Another important variable is the quality of government, which we will measure using the Worldwide Governance Indicators (Kaufmann et al., 2010). We are also interested in the effect of legitimacy on the acceptance of the measures adopted and, for that reason, we will include trust in political institutions as an explanatory variable. Sources for these variables include the European Social Survey (ESS) and the World Value Survey (WVS). Other political variables include the Effective Number of Parties (ENP), the distinction between

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majority and minority governments and the ideology of the government. We will also include controls for health policy, such as health expenditure per capita, or beds and doctors per capita. Socio-economic controls will include GDP per capita or aging of the population, among other potential variables related to the adoption of specific measures.

We consider two methods to analyse the data depending on the nature of the dependent variable. For variables measuring the cumulative number of confirmed cases at the time of the policy adoption we will use multiple regression models, since the dependent variable is continuous. For the other two types of dependent variables (measuring either the number of days between the first confirmed case and policy adoption and the duration of the adopted measure) we will use Cox proportional hazards models (Box-Steffensmeier and Jones, 2004; Cox, 1972).

3. Reflection of the state of the research

Our *qualitative research* proceeds within the set timetable and within the milestones we set.

1. According to our research design we conducted a systematic Literature review (Month 0-3).
2. We developed a theoretical framework (Month 3-6).
3. We selected a sample of economic measures (Month 6).
4. To illustrate how the framework can be applied in practice, we analysed decision-making and implementation of a specific measure (the Temporary Aid Programmes for small and medium sized businesses) in Germany and Spain (Month 6-8).
5. Having presented the theoretical framework and the first case studies during the ECPR conference in Prague (September 2023), we will fine-tune our coding scheme and will develop a questionnaire to obtain information from other project partners.
6. Afterwards we will map the decision-making and implementation processes to shed light on the multilevel dynamics (September 2023 to May 2024).
7. Next we will analyse the country profiles and decision-making and implementation of social, economic and fiscal measures during the COVID-19 crisis (June 2024).

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8. Using our definition of legitimacy above and operationalisation below, we will analyse the impact of multilevel governance on the legitimacy of crisis management and develop policy recommendations (June 2025).

Our *quantitative analysis* will proceed within the set timetable and milestones. We created an unbalanced panel data set that includes 15 periods (quarterly data, when available, from January 2020 to September 2022) and 31 European countries. During the next months, we will analyse the impact of the exogenous variables with a Multinomial Logit model.

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Project funded by

LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA No 101061550.

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Project funded by

LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under
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